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INCREASING ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN SCIENCE 9 THROUGH WORKSHEETS ON INTENTIONAL REFLECTION

ACTION RESEARCH
School Year 2022-2023

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic significantly disrupted education, exacerbating pre-existing learning gaps and highlighting the limitations of remote learning, particularly in under-resourced contexts. In response to these challenges, this action research focuses on improving the academic performance of Grade 9 students in Science through the use of Worksheets on Intentional Reflection (WIRe). WIRe is an intervention designed to enhance students' understanding of core scientific concepts by fostering reflective thinking after each lesson.

The study addresses the gap in prerequisite knowledge, specifically in chemistry concepts such as atomic structure and chemical behavior, which are foundational for Grade 9 topics like the Quantum Mechanical Model and compound properties. By employing WIRe, this research aims to close the knowledge gap and increase academic performance and engagement.

Forty Grade 9 students from Agoo National Vocational High School were divided into control and experimental groups. The experimental group utilized WIRe, while the control group followed traditional assessment methods. Pre-tests and post-tests were administered to both groups to measure the effectiveness of WIRe. Additionally, the study explored students' experiences with WIRe and its impact on their engagement levels.

Data were analyzed using frequency counts, mean, percentage, standard deviation, and Pearson r Moment Correlation to assess both academic performance and engagement. The results revealed that students in the experimental group demonstrated higher levels of engagement and improved performance compared to the control group. Specifically, the experimental group showed a significant increase in highly engaged learners, as well as enhanced comprehension of complex scientific concepts.

This study concludes that the use of WIRe as a reflective practice can be an effective tool in narrowing learning gaps and increasing academic performance in Science 9. By promoting intentional reflection, WIRe fosters deeper understanding and sustained engagement in the learning process, offering a potential solution to ongoing educational challenges in post-pandemic settings.

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